

Design and Simulation of Tunnel Lighting Systems Using Point-by-Point Model and Optimization of Luminaire Spacing

Amirhossein Tajmehr, Mahdi Nasiri Ghanjineh Ketab

1- AmirHossein Tajmehr, Tabriz University of Technology, Tajmehr.amir1382@iran.ir

2- Mahdi Nasiri Ghanjineh Ketab, Tabriz University of Technology, Nasirihadi260@gmail.com

Abstract

In this research, a specialized software was developed for the design and simulation of lighting in tunnels and underground mines. Utilizing a point-by-point model and supporting standard photometric data (IES and LDT), the software calculates the illuminance distribution across three zones: Entry, Transition, and Interior. The primary objective was to meet lighting requirements, including minimum illuminance (E_{min}) and uniformity (U_0), while reducing the number of luminaires and energy consumption. A binary search algorithm was employed to optimize the luminaire spacing, achieving a more economical design without compromising lighting quality. The results of a case study demonstrated that the software can calculate lighting parameters with high accuracy, identify areas requiring improvement, and reduce annual energy consumption through optimized luminaire spacing. The graphical and numerical outputs, including illuminance maps, central profiles, and PDF and CSV reports, facilitate both technical and economic analysis of the design.

Introduction

Proper lighting design in underground mines and tunnels is crucial for safety and operational efficiency, given challenging environmental factors such as dust, humidity, and restricted visibility. Compliance with international standards (e.g., CIE 88, EN 12464-2) and consideration of zone-specific requirements (Entry, Transition, Interior) are essential, alongside energy efficiency. However, current practice often relies on manual calculations or generic software lacking specialized capabilities, leading to inadequate uniformity analysis and suboptimal luminaire spacing. This study presents the development of a dedicated software tool for accurate simulation, analysis, and optimization of tunnel lighting systems, aiming to ensure full compliance with standards, minimize energy consumption, and deliver professional-grade analytical outputs.

Methods

A specialized software tool was developed for underground tunnel lighting design and optimization. The tool employs a point-by-point calculation method, utilizing standard IES and LDT photometric files to compute each luminaire's illuminance contribution across a defined calculation grid. After defining tunnel geometry and partitioning it into Entry, Transition, and Interior zones, key performance metrics minimum illuminance (E_{min}), average illuminance (E_{avg}), and overall uniformity (U_0)—are derived from the grid. A binary search algorithm optimizes luminaire spacing to minimize the number of fixtures and energy consumption while ensuring compliance with illuminance requirements. Outputs include contour maps, central illuminance profiles, numerical tables, and comprehensive PDF/CSV reports for technical and economic assessment.

Discussion and Conclusion

The developed software accurately computed illuminance distribution across Entry, Transition, and Interior zones, with all performance indicators meeting relevant standards. Contour maps and central profiles effectively identified areas with inadequate illumination or poor uniformity. Comparative analysis revealed that the binary search algorithm optimized luminaire spacing while maintaining required E_{min} and U_0 , resulting in reduced luminaire count and significant annual energy savings—particularly beneficial for long tunnels with extended operational periods. The tool's graphical and numerical outputs enable rapid scenario evaluation and informed engineering decisions. Ultimately, specialized lighting design software enhances safety, productivity, and economic performance in underground environments through precise calculations that simultaneously optimize visual conditions and energy efficiency.

References

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